

A STUDY ON WORKING WOMEN’S ATTITUDE TOWARDS INVESTMENT (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TIRUPPUR DISTRICT)

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Cite This Article: M. Amsaveni & Dr. M. Nithyadevi, “A Study on Working Women’s Attitude towards Investment (With Special Reference to Tiruppur District)”, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 2, Page Number 8-11, 2018.

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Abstract:

Women Investment is necessary for the individual to face unpredictable future in order to meet the emergencies in their family. In this paper, an attempt has been made to find out working women attitude towards investment. A sample of 100 respondent’s was randomly selected from Tiruppur District. Both primary and secondary data are collected for the study. Primary data collected are analyzed using simple percentage, ranking method and chi-square test. It is found that most of the working women’s are satisfied towards investment avenues. The study concludes that profitability was the first attitude of working women towards investment.

Key Words: Working, Investment, Attitude, Women, Finance, Profitability, Educated & Etc

Introduction:

In olden days women’s income is considered as a additional income within the family. But in present world more importance given to income earned by women. Mainly it is related to the share in the total household income and it also related to their control over the expenditure of the total household income. Women Investment is necessary for the individual to face unpredictable future in order to meet the emergencies in their family. Investment means sacrificing the some expenditure in order to satisfy the future commitments. The investment can be done in different ways by making bank deposits, post office, jewellery, shares, insurance etc., One of the best ways of investment is to create a monthly investment plan. According to women investor major features of an investment media are safety, profitability, speculation, tax benefit, liquidity, income stability, appreciation and easy transferability. From the point of view of women, investment is the accumulation of newly produced entities such as inventories, equipment, buildings etc.

Investment Avenues		
Lowest Investment Risk Instruments	Moderate Investment Risk Instruments	High Investment Risk Instruments
Bank Deposits	Corporate Bonds	Equity
Certificate of Deposits	Gold	Arts and collectibles
Commercial Papers	Exchange traded Funds	Non convertible Debentures
Treasury Bills	Convertible Bonds	Foreign Exchange Trading
Government Bonds	Real Estate	Mutual Funds

Review of Literature:

Ajmi Jy. A. (2008), evaluated the determinants of risk tolerance of individual investors from 1500 respondents with the help of the questionnaire. The research concluded that men are less risk averse than women, less educated investors are less likely to take risk and age factor is also important in risk tolerance and also investors are more risk tolerance than the less wealthy investors

Jagongo and Mutswenje (2014) analysed the factors influencing investment decisions at the Nairobi Stock Exchange. A sample of 42 respondents is selected for this study. The collected data are analysed using Descriptive analysis, friedman’s ranking test and Factor analysis. The most important factors that influence individual investment decisions were: reputation of the firm, firms status in industry, expected corporate earnings, profit and condition of statement, past performance firms stock, price per share, feeling on the economy and expected divided by investors.

Sonali Patil, Dr. Kalpana Nandawar (2014), examined the different avenues of investments as well as the factors while selecting the investment with the sample size of 40 salaried employees by conducting the survey through questionnaire in Pune, India. Primary data needed for the study is collected through personal interviews using a structured questionnaire. The collected primary data has been analyzed using percentage, chi-square test, and Person Correlation Coefficient. The study concludes that salaried employees consider the safety as well as good return on investment on regular basis.

Need of the Study:

- ✓ To know the present scenario of women investment.
- ✓ To know the attitude of investment among the working women in Tiruppur District.
- ✓ This study will help the investment avenues to customize the service according to the working women need.
- ✓ This study will also help the investment avenues to understand the expectation and experience of the working women.

Objective of the Study:

- ✓ To identify the investment pattern among working women.
- ✓ To study the level of attitude among working women towards investment avenues in Tiruppur District.

Hypothesis:

- ✓ There is no significant association between area and level of attitude.
- ✓ There is no significant association between age and level of attitude.
- ✓ There is no significant association between educational qualification and level of attitude.
- ✓ There is no significant association between Occupation and level of attitude.
- ✓ There is no significant association between marital status and level of attitude.
- ✓ There is no significant association between family income and level of attitude.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The results of the study are based upon the views expressed by the working women.
- ✓ The statistical method used to analyze the data has their own limitation.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Research Methodology:

Area of the Study: The research study was done in Tiruppur District.

Nature and Source of Data: The study is based on questionnaire method; primary data has been collected from various working women in Tiruppur District and the secondary data have been collected from related journals, Magazines and textbooks.

Sampling Used: 100 working women were selected by random sampling method.

Statistical Tools Used for the Study:

- ✓ Simple percentage analysis
- ✓ Ranking Method
- ✓ Chi-Square analysis

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Personal Profile

Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Area of residence		
Rural	34	34
semi rural	38	38
Urban	28	28
Age		
Less than 30 years	38	38
31-45 years	33	33
Above 45 years	29	29
Educational Qualification		
Upto SSLC	48	48
HSC	27	27
UG	25	25
Occupation		
Employee	65	65
Business	35	35
Marital status		
Married	37	37
Unmarried	63	63
Type of Family		
Nuclear	60	60
Joint	40	40
Monthly Income		
Upto Rs.15,000	40	40
Rs.15,000 to Rs.30,000	30	30
Rs. 30,000 to Rs. 45,000	30	30

Investing Years		
Less than 5 Years	25	25
6-10 Years	56	56
Above 10 Years	19	19

Table 1 describes the demographic profile of the working women. Out of 100 respondents who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (38%) of the working women belong to semi-urban area, (38%) of the working women age is less than 30 years, most (48%) of the working women studied upto SSLC, (65%) of the working women are employees, (63%) of the working women are unmarried, (60%) of the working women belong to nuclear family, (40%) of the working women monthly income is between Rs.15,000 to Rs.45,000 and (56%) of the working women are investing for a period of 6-10 years.

Table 2: Level of Attitude towards Investment Avenues

Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Low	16	16
Medium	29	29
High	55	55

From the above table, it shows that out of 100 working women (55%) of the working women level of attitude is high towards investment avenues, (29%) of the working women level of attitude is medium and (16%) of the working women level of attitude is low towards investment avenues.

Table 3: Working Women Motivational Factors towards Investment

Motivating Factors	Total Score	Rank
Safety	585	2
Liquidity	447	3
Prestige	369	4
Speculation	158	7
Stability	274	5
Transferability	597	6
Profitability	668	1

It is found from the above table, that profitability was the first factor which motivated the working women to create investment, safety was ranked as the second factor to choose investment media, Liquidity was ranked as third factor; Prestige was ranked as fourth factor; Stability was the fifth factor; Transferability was the sixth factor and speculation scored the seventh position.

Table 4: Relationship between Selected Demographic Profile and Working Women's Attitude towards investment

Variables	χ^2 Value	Table Value	Remarks
Area	5.654	9.488	NS
Age	10.675	9.488	NS
Educational Qualification	7.834	9.488	NS
Occupation	12.098	9.488	S
Marital Status	6.674	5.991	S
Monthly Income	11.832	9.488	S

* Significant at 5% percent level

Table 3 depicts the relationship between working women investors selected personal variables and level of attitude towards their investment. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is less than the table value at five percent level, there does not exist any significant association between area, age and educational qualification. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value at five percent level, there exists a significant association between occupation, marital status and monthly income.

Conclusions:

Today women have started realizing the importance of money and money's worth. Because of economic crisis has heightened women's recognition of the need to develop a financial plan that will meet long-term financial goals. In these days women are more involved than ever in their households' investment and financial decision making and they prepare a budget for the proposed expenses and compare it with the actual expenses met by them. It has become the present day need for working women in India to increase their wealth. The study concludes that most of the women are becoming high in financial literacy, it becomes easy for them to manage their portfolios on their own without their help of their family.

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